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WHEN TO SERVE ABROAD – THE HAGUE AND EU THE PERSPECTIVE

1. Introduction

The service of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil and commercial matters is of key importance for the proper initiation, conduct and conclusion of legal proceedings where one of the parties is in a country other than the country of the court seised. The movement of the consequent judgment also depends on service because deficiencies there may amount to a ground for refusal of enforceability/enforcement or for review. The service influences other institutes of private international law, such as access to certain instruments (for example the European) or grounds of jurisdiction.

The proper service guarantees the claimant access to justice and the defendant the right to a fair trial by giving him an opportunity to be heard. From the point of view of the functioning of the state, service is a condition for sound administration of justice, provided in a timely manner, which builds trust in the judicial system - a key factor in protecting the rule of law.

Traditionally, in the continental legal systems service is considered an expression of state sovereignty.¹ Therefore, each country can carry out service on its own territory, and when it is necessary to serve abroad- that foreign country must agree and cooperate. In this regard, during the years bilateral and multilateral treaties are concluded. The most important multilateral treaties are those adopted within the framework of the Hage Conference of Private International Law - the Convention of 15 November 1965 on the Service Abroad of Judicial and Extrajudicial Documents in Civil or Commercial Matters (Hague Convention).²

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¹ Hau, W. in Encyclopedia of Private International Law, 2017, p. 4238.

² <https://www.HagueConventionch.net/en/instruments/conventions/full-text/?cid=17>

In parallel, within the EU Member States are faced with the challenge of how to combine this traditional national approach with mutual trust, and the need to improve and speed up the transmission and service of judicial and extrajudicial documents. This is an important cornerstone of judicial cooperation in civil matters of cross-border implications developed pursuant to Art. 81 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).

The legal framework regarding the service of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil and commercial matters in the EU builds on the achievements of the Hague Convention. However, applying three regulations and elaborated further by the practice of the Court of Justice the EU (CJEU), the EU law gradually goes in directions that to some extent depart significantly from the model of the Hague Convention.

This article aims to examine one of the main questions, which over time finds different answers, namely - when a document in a civil and commercial matters should be served abroad. The focus will be on the solutions of the Hague Convention and the new Service of Documents Regulation.³ The goal is to compare these solutions and to assess which direction is more justified to be followed - the path of the Hague Convention or the Service of Documents Regulation.

2. Instruments

The cross-border service of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil and commercial cases is governed by national sources, sources of classical international law (bilateral and multilateral treaties) and by instruments of EU law.

The national framework is traditionally focused on the means of service within the respective country. It also contains rules for situations in which the addressee of the document is not personally or territorially connected to the state, has no known address, as well as rules governing unsuccessful service attempts.

The different treaties mainly govern the transmission of the documents, i.e. the cooperation between countries so that a document that concerns a pending case in one country can reach its addressee in another country. The general regulation in this regard is contained in the bilateral legal

³Regulation (EU) 2020/1784 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2020 on the service in the Member States of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil or commercial matters (service of documents) (recast).

aid treaties, as well as in the consular conventions, incl. in the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations.⁴

The need for specific, more detailed regulation of cross-border service was recognized at the dawn of the creation of the Hague Conference of Private International Law. The topic is covered by the three Civil Procedure Codes (from 1896,⁵ 1905⁶ and 1954⁷). Building upon them, the Hague Convention of 1965, still applicable today, was drawn up and adopted, currently binding 84 states. The scope of the convention concerns mostly the means of transmitting documents between states, not the service itself. The service is not defined. However, a remedy is provided in favor of the defendant if it does not appear (Articles 15 and 16).

Within the framework of EU law, service is subject to regulation in primary law - Article 81 TFEU, Article 47 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Charter)⁸ in relation with Article 6 of the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR).⁹ On a secondary law level three regulations are dedicated to the service of documents – Regulation 1348/2000¹⁰, 1393/2007¹¹ and the currently applicable one – Service of Documents Regulation. The first regulation was inspired by and built upon the Hague Convention of 1965. Further development expanded of the means of service, simplified the rules for translation and communication between the participants in the procedure using standard forms, and adapted to the modern technologies for communication. The most significant amendment that follows from the practice of the CJEU concerns the answer to the question posed in the article - when a document must be served in another Member State. Service issues are also raised by the other instruments of the EU law (e.g. Regulation Brussels Ia¹² in relation to the suspension and grounds for refusal of enforce-

⁴ https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/conventions/9_2_1963.pdf

⁵ <https://www.hcch.net/en/instruments/the-old-conventions/1896-civil-procedure>

⁶ <https://www.hcch.net/en/instruments/the-old-conventions/1905-civil-procedure-convention>

⁷ <https://www.hcch.net/en/instruments/conventions/full-text/?cid=33>

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A12012P%2FTXT>

⁹ https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/convention_ENG

¹⁰ Council regulation (EC) No 1348/2000 of 29 May 2000 on the service in the Member States of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil or commercial matters.

¹¹ Regulation (EC) No 1393/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 November 2007 on the service in the Member States of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil or commercial matters (service of documents), and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1348/2000.

¹² Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of

ment, Regulation Brussels IIb¹³ as regards the grounds for refusal, Regulation 1896/2006¹⁴ in the context of the minimum requirements for service, including no applicability if the defendant is not found, etc.). These last regulations and aspects are beyond the scope of the article.

3. When to serve abroad?

The answer to this question presupposes a review of the legal framework at the national level and at the level of the Hague Convention and EU law. The starting position is that, on the one hand, the defendant's right to know about the proceedings against him must be protected and he must be given an opportunity to defend himself. On the other hand, the defendant should not be allowed, by hiding, to block or unduly hinder the process, because in this way the right of the plaintiff to access to justice will be limited. These considerations to one degree or another are reflected at the normative level.

3.1. National law

At the national level, the regulation of service aims to provide the addressee with an actual opportunity to receive the document (personal service or service to a certain circle of close individuals). Then, to ensure access to court for the plaintiff, other types of service are used - the so-called substitute service (service to persons or in a way that contains a probability that the addressee will receive the document) and the so-called fictitious service (delivery in such a way that the probability of the addressee learning about the delivered document is practically null).

Also, the national sources stipulate when a given document must be served abroad.

For example, in Bulgaria the general principle is personal service (Article 38(1) CPC). However, the service may be effected through other person and by placing the documents to the file of the case or by sticking on the notification (Article 38(2) CPC). The final solution is the public notification in the State Gazette (Article 38(3) CPC).

12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters (recast).

¹³ Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 on jurisdiction, the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, and on international child abduction (recast).

¹⁴ Regulation (EC) No 1896/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 creating a European order for payment procedure.

3.2. *Hague Conventions*

The Hague Convention aims to create appropriate means to ensure that judicial and extrajudicial documents be served abroad (see preamble). The emphasis is on the means of service, not the service itself, which is not defined. The specified delivery methods must, as highlighted in the preamble, bring to the notice of the addressee the documents in sufficient time. Thus, the Hague Convention aims to improve the organization of mutual judicial assistance and for that purpose, to simplify and speed up the procedure.

In this context, the provisions of Article 1, paragraph 1 of the Hague Convention provide that it applies in all cases ... *where there is occasion to transmit a ... document for service abroad*. The key question that this provision poses is who determines whether there is an occasion to transmit in another country - the law of the court seised or the Hague Convention. The answer that prevails is that whether a document must be served abroad is given by *lex fori* - i.e. only if the law of the court, which hears the claim, requires the document to be served in another country and it is the contracting party, then the methods established in the Hague Convention will be applied. Conversely, if national law provides for other methods of service (e.g. to a representative who is located in that country, or in the case of an address - by sticking), they prevail, and it may not be necessary to serve abroad in compliance with the Hague Convention.

This view is based on arguments from the history of the adoption and application of the Hague Convention, as well as from a comparative law perspective.

Already in the report to the draft convention from 1964, it is explicitly stated that *the issue of whether the Convention should be applied in a particular case is indeed determined by the law of the court seised*¹⁵. In the same sense are the statements made during the diplomatic session on the acceptance of the Hague Convention from 1964.¹⁶ Subsequently, in 1989 the Report of the Special Commission on the Application of the Hague Convention stated that ...*The principle that the forum is to decide this question [i.e., whether documents should be transmitted for service abroad] under its own law was broadly accepted, although the danger of permitting domestic service upon a person who had not been expressly designated as an agent to receive service of process was recognized*¹⁷. The conclusions and recommendations of

¹⁵ Report of the 1964 SC (op. cit. note 25), p. 81, HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 15.

¹⁶ Op. cit.

¹⁷ Report on the work of the Special Commission of 1989 on the operation of the Hague

the special commission from 2003 explicitly emphasize the optional nature of the Hague Convention¹⁸. In this sense are the interpretations that are given in the 2014 Practical Handbook.¹⁹

From a comparative legal point of view, two leading court decisions are of great significance - one from the Netherlands, the other from the USA.

The first one is *Segers and Rufa BV v. Mabanafit GmbH* (“Mabanafit”) by the Supreme Court of the Netherlands (Hoge Raad).²⁰ In the given case, the appeal against the decision of the Court of Appeal in the Hague was served on the opposite party - a German company - through its lawyer in the Hague. This possibility existed under the civil procedure law of the Netherlands which allowed the service of notice required upon appeal of a lower court judgment to be made upon the attorney at whose office the addressee had elected domicile in the lower court proceedings.²¹ The respondent did not appear, and a default judgment against it was issued. Hoge Raad held that *the issue of whether a document needed to be transmitted abroad for service must be determined according to the law of the forum*.

The other one is *Volkswagen Aktiengesellschaft v Schlunk* (“Schlunk”)²² by the Supreme Court of the United States. This case was brought by Mr. Schlunk against Volkswagen USA and its parent company - Volkswagen Germany for product (car) damages. The lawsuit against the German parent company was filed through the Volkswagen USA, which under the laws of the state of Illinois, where the case is pending, appears as an agent for service in Illinois, even though it had not been expressly appointed for such a purpose. Thus, according to the law of the seised court, service abroad was not necessary, which is why the Hague Convention did not apply. This issue came to Supreme Court of the United States, who ruled that *if the internal law of the forum state defines the applicable method of serving process as requiring the transmittal of documents abroad, then the Hague Service Convention*

Conventions of 15 November 1965 on the Service Abroad of Judicial and Extrajudicial Documents in Civil or Commercial Matters and of 18 March 1970 on the Taking of Evidence Abroad in Civil or Commercial Matters”, p. 5, <https://assets.HagueConventionch.net/docs/e8456534-1ba4-4bc9-ade8-bcf3a7b85c5d.pdf>

¹⁸ Report on the work of the Special Commission of 2003, <https://assets.HagueConventionch.net/docs/0edbc4f7-675b-4b7b-8e1c-2c1998655a3e.pdf>

¹⁹ HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 13.

²⁰ *Segers and Rufa BV v. Mabanafit GmbH*, 28 I.L.M. 1584, 1585 (1989). *Segers and Rufa BV v. Mabanafit GmbH*, HR 27 June 1986, NJ 1987, p. 764; RvdW 1986,

²¹ HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 13.

²² 486 U.S. 694 (1988). 486 U.S. 694; 108 S. Ct. 2104 (1988); I.L.M. 1988, p. 1093, annotated in: Am. J. Int’l L. 1988, p. 816; IPRax 1989, p. 313.

applies. Thus, because the service was effected within the United States, the Hague Convention did not apply.²³

The described interpretation is adopted by the Supreme Court of Victoria and New South West in Australia,²⁴ Canada,²⁵ as well as, despite some contradictions,²⁶ in Germany. There, since 1994, there has been even a decision of the German Constitutional Court, which expressly accepted that the Hague Convention applies only when domestic law requires service abroad.²⁷ The German Bundesgerichtshof has also shared the same view,²⁸

From what has been stated so far, stems that the Hague Convention does not define the concept of service, i.e. does not set any formal requirements for it, nor does it govern the conditions for ordinary service. The Hague Convention does not determine when a given document must be served in a country other than the country of the court deciding on the merits. This answer is given by the law of the court seized. Essentially, the Hague Convention mainly regulates the transmission of documents²⁹. If, according to the law of the court seized, the service must be carried out in another country, a party to the Hague Convention, then its system must be followed. Afterwards, it provides an alternative options for service through Central Authorities (Articles 2-6), diplomatic and consular representatives (Articles 8-9) or direct service (Article 10), and allows the states to agree on other methods for transmission of documents (Article 11), i.e. to conclude other bilateral or multilateral agreements, incl. to adopt acts at EU level. Thus, the Hague Convention retains the possibility to use national service (e.g. substitute or even fictitious). At the same time, in order not to excessively limit the rights of the addressee of the document, the Hague Convention provides remedies in Articles 15 and 16. They apply if the defendant fails to appear when the summons or other equivalent document should have been sent abroad to be served under the Hague Convention.

²³ HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 14-15.

²⁴ *Nieuwersteeg v. Colonia Versicherungen AG*, HR 2 February 1996, NJ 1997, p. 26 and HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 16.

²⁵ HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 16.

²⁶ *Drucksache des Bundestags* Nr. 8/217 of 22 March 1977, p. 41 and Geimer, G. Neuordnung des internationalen Zustellungsrechts, Vorschläge für eine neue Zustellungsconvention, 1999, p. 180.

²⁷ BVerfG, 7 December 1994, NJW 1995, p. 649.

²⁸ *BGH*, NJW 1999, 1187 (1188), *Fleischhauer*, IPRax 2000, 12 ff. and *BGH*, NJW 1999, 2442 (2443).

²⁹ HCCH, Practical Handbook on the Operation of the Service Convention, 2016, p. 22.

3.3. Regulations

3.3.1. Old Regulations

The repealed Regulations 1348/2000 and 1393/2007 provided that they apply where a judicial or extrajudicial document has to be transmitted from one Member State to another for service there (Article 1, para.1). This language, apparently borrowed from Hague Convention, justified the interpretation that it was not EU law, but the law of the Member State where the case was pending, to determine whether a document had to be served abroad. Only if this law provides for service abroad then the Regulation establishes the way this is to happen,³⁰ As a result, the possibility of applying national methods of service that have a fictitious nature (e.g. the previously known in France institute of the so-called *remise au parquet*) remained. The legal theory argued against such an interpretation, stating that it is incompatible with EU law, mainly because it is a violation of Art. 6 of the ECHR and of Art. 47 Charter and that it affects addressees who live in another EU Member State in a discriminatory manner,³¹

3.3.2. Case law of CJEU

The EU Court clarified and gave an answer to the problem that arose in the application of the repealed Regulation 1393/2007.

In case C-325/11 *Adler* of December 19, 2012 the CJEU had to decide on a case where claimants residing in Germany seised the Polish court who asked them to communicate to it a representative in Poland authorized to accept the service of judicial documents. The Polish court also inform the claimants

³⁰ Dominelli, S. Current and Future Perspectives on Cross-border Service of Documents. *Aracne*. 2018, p. 50, Мусева, Б. Проблеми при връчването на съдебни и извънсъдебни документи по граждански и търговски дела според Регламент 1348/2000, Регламент 1393/2007 и българския гражданско процесуален кодекс. – в: Международното частно право и някои правила от част седма на ГПК в светлината на общностното право. С. Силеа, 2008, с. 30, Musielak/Voit, *Zivilprozessordnung: ZPO*, 19. Auflage 2022, EuZustVO, Art. 1 Anwendungsbereich, Rn. 3, LG Hamburg, 12.03.2013-335, unalex DE-3196, Cass. Civ. sez.19-05-2014 – 10945, unalex IT-760.

³¹ Heiderehoff, B. Fiktive Zustellung und Titelmobilität. - *IPRax*, 2013, №4, p. 313, Roth, H. *Remise au parquet und Auslandszustellung nach dem Haager Zustellungsübereinkommen von 1965* - *IPRax*, 2000, Nr. 6, p. 487, Lindacher, W. *Europäisches Zustellungsrecht- Die VO (EG) Nr.1348/2000* Fortschritt, Auslegungsbedarf, Problemausblendung – *Zeitschrift für Zivilrecht*, 2001, Nr. 2, p. 189, Stadler, A. *Neues Europäisches Zustellungsrecht* - *IPRax*, 2001, Nr. 6, 514-516, Bajons, E. *Internationale Zustellung und Recht auf Verteidigung*, In: *Wege zur Globalisierung des Rechts; Festschrift für Rolf Schutze zum 65. Geburtstag*, München: C.H. Beck, 1999, p. 55.

that in case they failed to do so, any documents addressed to them would have been added to the file case and deemed to be effectively served as established by the Polish Code of Civil Procedure (Article 1135). The claimants refused to comply with the court's request. Consequently, the court's notice about the date of the hearing and the counterparts' briefs were included in the file and deemed to have been effectively served. The claimants did not appear to the hearing, the claim was eventually dismissed and lacking any challenge, the judgment became final. Afterwards, the claimants requested a trial to resume due to not receiving judicial documents, in violation of the EU non-discrimination laws. The District Court refused, stating Polish law complied with EU law. The Regional Court overturned this, finding Polish procedure violated EU regulation. The District Court disagreed and halted proceedings to seek clarification from the CJEU on whether serving documents in such a manner is permissible under EU law. CJEU established that the applicability of the Regulation is determined autonomously and independently of the national law of the court seised. Point 25 of the judgment explicitly stated that *where the person to be served with the judicial document resides abroad, the service of that document necessarily comes within the scope of Regulation No 1393/2007 and must, therefore, be carried out by the means put in place by the regulation to that end, as provided for by Article 1(1) thereof.* Hence, the Regulation answers both the question of "whether" and the question of "how" it should be served in another Member State if the addressee of the document lives there. Therefore, as follows from the operative part of this judgment, national provisions on fictitious service are inadmissible which provide, that *judicial documents addressed to a party whose place of residence or habitual abode is in another Member State are placed in the case file, and deemed to have been effectively served, if that party has failed to appoint a representative who is authorised to accept service and is resident in the first Member State, in which the judicial proceedings are taking place.* The only two exceptions where the Regulation would not apply are: a) to service of a document on the party's authorised representative in the Member State where the proceedings are taking place regardless of the place of residence of that party and b) where the address of the person to be served with the document is not known.

Following the *Alder* judgement, Article 1135 of the Polish Code of Civil Procedure was amended. The Bulgarian CPC contains a provision identical to the one of the former Article 1135 of the Polish Code of Civil Procedure (Article 40(1)). Unfortunately, it has not amended yet.

As explained, the mandatory application of the Regulation is correct if the addressee of the document's lives/habitually resides in another Member State and his or her address is not unknown.

The concepts of *living, having a place of residence or habitual residence*, as well as the *address is unknown* raise numerous subsequent questions regarding their exact content and the obligations of the court and/or the parties in connection with their establishment. Unsurprisingly, some of these issues also end up at the CJEU. They will be analyzed below in connection with the assessment of the presence of a known (unknown) address.

3.3.3. Service of Documents Regulation

The new Service of Documents Regulation preserves the existing legal norms while providing some linguistic amendments without, however, legislating against the outcomes given by the EU Court in the *Adler* case.

More specifically, Article 1, paragraph 1 of the Regulation provides that it applies to the cross-border service of judicial and extrajudicial documents in civil or commercial cases. Recital 5 specifies that such cross-border service should be considered as service from one Member State to another Member State. Based on this wording, it is assumed that the European legislator clearly states that service within the EU is only to be carried out pursuant to the Regulation³².

In the Commission's proposal, which started the negotiation process for the adoption of the new Regulation, it was explicitly proposed to provide for a clarification that it applies to service of judicial documents on persons domiciled in a Member State other than the one where the judicial proceedings take place (Art. 1, par. 1, b. "a" of the proposal). As the Commission points out, in *doing this, the Regulation tries to put an end to the current bad practice in which defendants in another Member States are served in the territory of the Member State of origin through alternative or fictitious methods of service of documents, as permitted by the procedural law of the Member State of origin, irrespective of the information on the foreign address of the defendant at the disposal of the court or judicial authority seised with the proceedings. With the new scope wording, courts would not be able to carve such situations out of the scope of the Regulation by simply qualifying the service of the documents as 'domestic'*.³³ During the negotiations, this issue turned out to be quite controversial, probably also due to the use of the term "domicile", that is new for this Regulation, which, when applying the Brussels Ia Regulation for natural persons, has a different content in different Member States (Article 62) and can lead to ambiguities in view of the scope of the Service of Documents Regulation.

³² Richter, J. Internationale Klagezustellung nach der neugefassten EuZustVO – IPRAX, 2022, Nr. 5, p. 434.

³³ COM (2018) 379 final, c. 13.

Thus, there is no provision in the final text of the Service of Documents Regulation that explicitly specifies when a document must be served in another Member State. At the same time, Recital 7 clarifies this issue by emphasizing the values that the European Commission wanted to uphold in its proposal. Pursuant to it, where an addressee has no known address for service in the forum Member State but has one or more known addresses for service in one or more other Member States, the document should be transmitted to such other Member State for service under this Regulation. This situation should not be construed as domestic service within the forum Member State. The prohibitions on treating such service as domestic and in particular the application of fictitious methods of service to it, such as service by posting an announcement on the court notice board or by depositing the document in the court file, are expressly included as examples. It is worth noting that the precise content of the concept of “known address” is again crucial, which will be analyzed below.

The new version regarding the application of the Regulation is supposed to be interpreted in relation to the repealed Regulation and the practice of the CJEU. The idea set by the Commission to ensure the application of the regulation when serving a person who lives in another Member State, by limiting the extension of “domestic” service for similar scenarios, should also be taken into account. Thus, it can be concluded that from the presented legal framework at the level of EU law, service must take place in another Member State whenever the addressee of the document lives there. The methods of service are those established in the Regulation. National methods of service are inadmissible, which have the effect of excluding the obligation to serve the documents to the other Member State.

3.3.4. Follow up Questions

From the analysis above it became clear that the existence of a “known address” is of key importance for service in another Member State under the Regulation. This concept poses many questions, the most important of which can be reduced to two: what is an unknown address (here reduced further to the question of whether it is related to a formal registration in a given country or to the place where the person actually resides) and is the court obliged to make efforts to look for an address in another Member State (if yes, what should it actually do (*ex officio* or with the assistance of the parties)).

Two decisions of the Court of the EU shed light on these questions.

The first one – *C-327/10 Hypoteční banka*³⁴ – refers to a situation in

³⁴ CJEU in *Hypoteční banka* C-327/10, ECLI:EU:C:2011:745.

which a defendant - a natural person - had a last known place of residence (address) in the Czech Republic, but at the time of the initiation of the case in this country, this person no longer resided in that place, accordingly, the court seised accepted that his domicile and current address are unknown (points 2 and 36). The CJEU gave an answer to the question of whether the seised court can continue the proceedings in order to avoid a situation of denial of justice for the claimant if it not be possible to determine the defendant's domicile. Such a possibility is established in the former Brussels I Regulation (Art. 26, par. 2) and in the Brussels Ia Regulation (Art. 28, par. 2). According to CJEU, these provisions, which are identical, should be understood in the sense that a court having jurisdiction pursuant to that regulation may reasonably continue proceedings, in the case where it has not been established that the defendant has been enabled to receive the document instituting the proceedings, only if all necessary steps have been taken to ensure that the defendant can defend his interests. To that end, the court seised of the matter must be satisfied that all investigations required by the principles of diligence and good faith have been undertaken to trace the defendant (point 52).

The second case – C-292/10 *G*³⁵ – concerns a matter relating to tort brought in Germany against an individual who had an address in the Netherlands, but when served, the documents were returned marked ‘Unknown at this address’. The court hearing the case in Germany made an inquiry to the Consulate of the Kingdom of the Netherlands in Munich. It stated, that the person was not listed in any population register in the Netherlands (point 29). Attempts were also made to deliver the documents to different addresses, which were also unsuccessful. In this context, the German court summoned the defendant under its national law by publishing the document for the initiation of the proceedings in the court according to Art. 185-188 of the German Code of Civil Procedure. The question addressed to CJEU is whether this national provision, applicable when the defendant's whereabouts in the Union territory are not known and it cannot otherwise be established where he is currently residing, contradicts Art. 6, par. 1 TEU in connection with Art. 47, par. 2 of Charter, as well as other provisions of EU law.

In its answer, the CJEU started from the understanding that proceedings leading to the delivery of judicial decisions have to take place in such a way that the rights of the defence are observed (point 47). However, this right must be implemented with due regard to the applicant's right to bring an action before a court to rule on the merits of his claim (point 48), which in practice means that it may be subject to restrictions (point 49). This restric-

³⁵ CJEU in C-292/10 *G*, ECLI:EU:C:2012:142.

tion, on its part, is only permissible if it corresponds to the objectives of public interest, which in this case is assumed to be the need to avoid situations of denial of justice that a claimant would face should it not be possible to determine the defendant's domicile (point 50).

Hence, referring to the previous judgment – C-327/10 *Hypoteční banka a.s.* - The CJEU accepted, referring again to Art. 26, par. 2 of the Brussels I Regulation (art. 28, par. 2 of the Brussels Ia Regulation) that the court could reasonably continue the proceedings only if all necessary steps have been taken to ensure that the defendant can defend his interests. To that end, the court seised of the matter must be satisfied that all investigations required by the principles of diligence and good faith have been undertaken to trace the defendant (point 55). As an additional argument, the CJEU also uses the practice of the ECHR under Art. 6, paragraph 1 of the ECHR, which does not preclude 'summons by public notice', provided that the rights of those concerned are properly protected³⁶. All this, however, again, is only possible if all inquiries required by the principles of diligence and good faith are undertaken to locate the defendant.

Several conclusions follow from these judgments of the CJEU. Service must take place in the Member State where the person actually resides in order to have an effective opportunity to defend himself. If, in the course of the proceedings, it is established that the person does not reside at the address indicated in the case (or at the address at which he is formally entered in the population database), but is in another Member State, the court seised has no right to directly proceed to national (fictitious) service. It is required first to ensure that efforts are made to discover the actual address/domicile/residence of the defendant as required by the principles of diligence and good faith. How exactly (gathering information from relatives, neighbours, employer, diplomatic/consular representation, use of telephone, e-mail, modern communication technologies, etc.) and exactly who (the court alone or with the help of the parties/other state authorities) should undertake those efforts is a matter left to national procedural law. EU law sets the framework - discovering the addressee of the document and making efforts that are not formal, but possible, logical and with the potential to give him an effective opportunity to familiarize himself with the documents to be served.

In addition, according to Art. 7 of the Service of Documents Regulation, Member States are obliged to provide assistance in determining an unknown address at the request of another Member State in, choosing one of the following ways:

³⁶ ECtHR Decision of 10 April 2003 in the case of *Nunes Dias v. Portugal*, Recueil des arrêts et décisions 2003-IV.

- providing for designated authorities to which transmitting agencies may address requests on the determination of the address of the person to be served³⁷;
- allowing persons from other Member States to submit requests, including electronically, for information about addresses of persons to be served directly to domicile registries or other publicly accessible databases by means of a standard form available on the European e-Justice Portal;
- providing detailed information, through the European e-Justice Portal, on how to find the addresses of persons to be served.³⁸

Member States shall provide information on which means of assistance they have chosen incl. indicate the relevant authorities and their contact details (Article 7, par. 2, b. “a” and “b”). Member States also specify whether the authorities of the Member State addressed submit, on their own initiative, requests to domicile registries or other databases for information about addresses in cases where the address indicated in the request for service is not correct (Art. 7, par. 2, b. “in “). All information in this regard is available and accessible on the European e-Justice Portal in the section “European Judicial Atlas on Civil Matters”, respectively in the part entitled “Service of documents (recast)”.³⁹

The introduced uniform obligation to provide assistance in the search of an unknown address is a novelty. It is dictated by the desire of the European legislator to better protect the right of access to a court of the addressee of the documents in civil and commercial cases with cross-border implications. Essentially, this new provision extends the scope of the Service of Documents Regulation, insofar as it does not allow the court seised to assume that the address of a person is unknown and to apply its national rules for service before the assistance in address enquiries in another Member State has been used.

The possibility of assistance in finding an address does not exhaust the efforts that could potentially be made with a view to complying with the principal diligence and of good faith. This is an additional option which, because it exists, can reasonably be expected to be used.

³⁷ For example the *bailliff* in Belgium, Lithuania, and Luxembourg, the district court in Czechia and Slovakia, the Ministry of Interior in Croatia.

³⁸ For example, Central Population Register in Austria, the mayor of a municipality, town or city in Poland, or the registration authorities in Germany.

³⁹ https://e-justice.europa.eu/38580/BG/serving_documents_recast

4. Conclusion

The conclusion of EU law is that the answer to the question of whether a document must be served in another Member State is given by the Regulation (except in the case of an unknown address and service to a representative), and not by the national law of the court seised. This interpretation is the opposite of what exists in the Hague Convention. This begs the question, which resolution is better?

From the brief explanation above, it can be seen that EU law in the last more than 20 years has developed in a direction that protects the right to a fair trial to a greater extent. Considering actual residence instead of formal registrations and access to substituted and fictitious service arguably provides more effective access to justice for the defendant. The involvement of the court and the parties in searching for an address, when there are clues in this direction, also contributes to a better sound administration of justice.

Is it possible that the development within the framework of EU law, built on the Hague Convention, will affect its development? From the point of view of ensuring the right to a fair trial, this would be a positive result. Since the Hague Convention unites a much larger number of states, as well as since amending a convention is a very complex and difficult process, positive legal development in this direction can hardly be expected. A step forward would be for the solutions withheld at the level of EU law to be used as a model for the development of national procedural law. With the help of new technologies and the traces that individuals leave in electronic environments, ascertaining of whereabouts is likely to become easier over time.

The law cannot and should not remain indifferent, and the court should not look for the simplest and easiest way to start, conduct and conclude its case as if the people don't move, as if the case has no international element and regardless of whether the defendant will be able to defend himself effectively.

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